

→ [Noncoding DNA and the teem theory of inheritance, emotions and innate behaviour](#)

MIMS 4.31 - Storage of Karma and the “language” of ‘junk’ DNA

A Charge Distributive Network hypothesis about why junk DNA conforms to Zipf’s
Law

September 2022

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the author wishes to explore the potentiality of the transcription of events and trauma into the non-coded DNA, as a possible description of the storage of karma (in observance of the Law of Causality) in the k region, both located in the northern pole of the Big-G + wuxingmingtu, as per the previous study. The discussion of Zipf’s Law and TEEM theory are sidebars to the philosophical pursuit, which has been also explored in three parts of episodes.^{1 2 3} The main interest is in the actions of the CDNs in the transcription and/or elimination of health karma, as evidence for this mechanism. Our interests extend so far as observations on religious purity and breathing exercises.

Key Words: MIMS - noncoded DNA - karma - Charge Distributive Networks

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QW-Zda002dU>

 #72 Do thoughts have layers? What is The Geometry of Consciousness? The Holographic Snake

²

<https://rumble.com/v1kbg95-the-pulse-episode-79-the-mims-of-junk-dna-and-karma-pre-hypothetical-discus.html>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YjfYv0B4pCQ> Symbols of the Universe, Creating Life thru Auroras & Jumping ...

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Hancock's Assertion of the Flam Hypothesis?	3
Zipf's Law	5
TEEM Theory	9
Paradoxes	10
Case Studies	10
MIMS 4.31 - the Hypothesis	14
Test Proposal	14
Sin, Karma, Illness, Jesus, and the Religious Search for Purity	15
Conclusion	18
Appendix A - the Acres of Diamonds	20
Appendix B - The HuffPo Before and After Slides	21
References	26

Hancock's Assertion of the Flam Hypothesis?

In "Supernatural,"⁴ G. Hancock made the assertion that research had been done to prove that the "junk" or non-coded DNA, as per the Human Genome Project⁵, was conforming to Zipf's Law⁶. His assertion, to be frank, seemed like an attempt to justify prolonged use of psychedelics, given his self-disclosed pseudo-addiction to Ayahuasca. But the book had laid out an excellent groundwork for the idea of the mind as a transponder-receiver aka transceiver of some form of Universal (and fractal?) consciousness.

In the MIMS 2.0, a "Big G" diagram was introduced⁷, quickly raising the bar on the philosophy⁸ to deal with spirit and consciousness, given the assertions of 'digitizing' spirit through the ambitions of the bio-psychology as a concrete reality. It isn't that we *cannot* accept spirituality - it properly fits into the MIMS 2.2 category - given we have an ongoing effort to codify the Threefold Sciences⁹. However, in the MIMS 1¹⁰ and 2 standards¹¹, the need is to service the neuroscientific community, which relies on a materio-reductionist abstractification of the more thoroughly resolved and lucid reality of anecdotal experience. Reliance upon electro-magnetic and radiative equipment, designed with the mind (and spirit? Via intuition?) and then interpreted through the mind, is a bit philosophically specious. But it is their paradigm, at present, across most theorems¹². Nevertheless, to understand Hancock's transceiver ideas (which he may have borrowed from others, T. McKenna comes to mind first) one needs to accept that there is a consciousness interface in the MIMS, and that it is the *L* power¹³, and we do **not** mean "Love is Watching" as per B. Dougherty (the Dougherty Set), although we do not assert it is *not* this, either. The *L* power is a mytho-historical, scientifico-mathematico, religio-thoological, and psychological reality which **cannot** be discounted¹⁴. The data on the *L* power is too voluminous to speak of, but our sole interest, via the intersection of the 5 and 8, is the Law of Causality (via Fire Phase).

Moreover, we are interested in the empirical evidence asserted. It appears to be based on Flam¹⁵; and there is of course, contrary peer review from Chatzidimitriou-Dreismann¹⁶. It may also be Niyogi¹⁷. Recently, there is the work of Forte et al.¹⁸, which speaks on seismic tomography as well, using Zipf's Law¹⁹. We do not have the space, nor inclination, to reply to all of these and peer-review them here, point by point. However,

⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Supernatural-Publisher-Disinformation-Company-Revised/dp/B004QOK53I/>

⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Human-Genome-Project>

⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/science/information-theory/Linguistics>

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

⁹ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

¹⁰

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPE_MC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

¹¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

¹²

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/new-perspectives-on-type-identity/brief-history-of-neurosciences-actual-influences-on-mindbrain-reductionism/2F3B158F1631B62796C05C4860BC5DE5>

¹³ The Lord: https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

¹⁴ The discussion of the Dirac Delta "truth" vector cannot be ignored, given the facts of needing dirac delta to describe electricity.

¹⁵ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7973718/>

¹⁶ <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/24/9/1676/1157737>

¹⁷ <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/6634>

¹⁸ <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.268.5209.386>

¹⁹ This introduces some **excellent** outlets for EPEMC to interface with MIMS directly through this 4.3X standard and the electrogeology (EG) and HEGEME theory outlets.

suffice it to say the science is ongoing, contentious, and potentially fraught with difficulty. More to the point, it might also be that the Uncertainty Principle, as discussed in MIMS 2.21.1 is a bit affecting in “what is seen.” Nevertheless, assume that only one camp is right. The one we will take, arbitrarily, for correctness is that the non-coded DNA conforms to Zipf’s law of linguistics, and that the mind is a transceiver. In fact, as per the author’s own research²⁰, it might be that the DNA’s electromagnetic and known antenna behaviors^{21 22 23}, are direct scalar connections or as Dougherty/Muller/McKenna assert, a quantum tunneling mechanism. The author simply relies upon the concepts of antenna-signal theory²⁴, and nevertheless, plenty of reasons may exist for the transceiver DNA, nerve, and not the least of which has to do with the author’s fractal-circuit theory: Charge Distributive Networks²⁵.

Figure 1 - Charge Distribute Network semi-symbolic fractal-wave-theory compliant circuit diagram; credit: author

²⁰

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases

²¹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21457072/>

²² <https://www.sciencealert.com/scientists-have-made-the-tiniest-antenna-ever-using-dna>

²³ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/50986117_DNA_is_a_fractal_antenna_in_electromagnetic_fields

²⁴ <https://www.antenna-theory.com/basics/main.php>

²⁵

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_structure_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

Zipf's Law

Noncoding DNA, Zipf's Law, and Language

Faye Flam (Research News, 25 Nov. 1994, p. 1320) reports that Eugene Stanley and his colleagues (1) have found that Zipf's law (2) applies somewhat better to noncoding than to protein-coding DNA sequences. The article implies that the statistical difference between protein-coding and noncoding DNA sequences is a surprising new discovery and that noncoding DNA resembles some sort of language.

The fact that nucleotide sequences of protein-coding regions have a different statistical structure than those of various kinds of noncoding regions (such as introns or intergenic spacers) has been well known since at least 1981 (3). In fact, many routine methods for discriminating between coding and noncoding DNA regions are based on such differences (4). It is therefore difficult to appreciate the alleged novelty of the findings of Stanley and his colleagues.

Zipf's distribution is not specific to language. Zipf himself said that it is far more general. Diverse examples of log-rank distributions that fit Zipf's law include relative sizes of cities (2, p. 416), income (2, p. 484; 5), number of species per genus (2, p. 231), and number of papers per scientist in a

given field of research (2, p. 514; 6). There is no reason to conclude that a general population is a language even if a sample drawn from this population is characterized by Zipf's distribution.

The oligonucleotide frequency distribution in noncoding DNA does not appear to fit Zipf's law any better than does the distribution in coding regions. As may be seen clearly in the figure accompanying Flam's article, both log-rank distributions are similar and both display a nonlinear, rather than a linear, trend. In both cases, only a portion of the range can be approximated by a linear function when the data are plotted on log-log coordinates. A reasonable conclusion is that both coding and noncoding regions fit Zipf's law rather poorly, if at all.

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6. A. J. Lotka, *J. Washington Acad. Sci.* **16**, 317 (1926).

Corrections and Clarifications

In the report "Continent-ocean chemical heterogeneity in the mantle based on seismic tomography" by Alessandro M. Forte *et al.* (21 Apr., p. 386), note 14 (p. 388) should have included the following sentence at the end. "We note, however, that this classical measure of significance does not take into account the red spectrum of the observed nonhydrostatic geoid, whose harmonic coefficients cannot be properly regarded as a random distribution; therefore, the statistical significance of the measured correlation coefficient is possibly less than 99%."

Figure 2 - Article regarding original Flam research; credit: Konopka et al./PubMed

A Note of Zipf's Law, Natural Languages, and Noncoding DNA Regions

Author(s)

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Abstract

In Phys. Rev. Letters (73:2), Mantegna et al. conclude on the basis of Zipf rank frequency data that noncoding DNA sequence regions are more like natural languages than coding regions. We argue on the contrary that an empirical fit to Zipf's "law" cannot be used as a criterion for similarity to natural languages. Although DNA is a presumably "organized system of signs" in Mandelbrot's (1961) sense, and observation of statistical features of the sort presented in the Mantegna et al. paper does not shed light on the similarity between DNA's "grammar" and natural language grammars, just as the observation of exact Zipf-like behavior cannot distinguish between the underlying processes of tossing an M-sided die or a finite-state branching process.

Date issued

1995-03-01

Figure 3 - Abstract: "A Note of Zipf's Law, Natural Languages, and Noncoding DNA Regions"; credit: Niyogi & Berwick/Academic

Please note these screenshots are shared to show both the abstracts and ALL details of citation as well as demonstrate something about the Peer-Review Cult²⁶: they expect conformity of all researchers, but in no way provide a standard amongst each other nor ease of access. This increases the author's view that much of the PRC is about control and prestige, rather than the pursuit of facts and truth. Which is no reflection on these articles in particular, but on the journals themselves.

Note to journals: fair use. Author took the screenshots which are © Sf. R. Careaga.

Lack of Biological Significance in the ‘Linguistic Features’ of Noncoding DNA—A Quantitative Analysis

C. A. Chatzidimitriou-Dreismann , R. M. F. Streffer, D. Larhammar

Nucleic Acids Research, Volume 24, Issue 9, 1 May 1996, Pages 1676–1681,
<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/24.9.1676>

Published: 01 May 1996 **Article history** ▼

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Abstract

Recently, the application of two statistical methods (related to Zipf's distribution and Shannon's redundancy), called ‘linguistic’ tests, to the primary structure of DNA sequences of living organisms has excited considerable interest. Of particular importance is the claim that noncoding DNA sequences in eukaryotes display specific ‘linguistic’ features, being reminiscent of natural languages. Furthermore, this implies that noncoding regions of DNA may carry some new, thus far unknown, biological information which is revealed by these tests. In this paper these claims are tested quantitatively. With the aid of computer simulations of natural DNA sequences, and by applying the same ‘linguistic’ tests to both natural and artificial sequences, we investigate in detail the reasons of the appearance of the claimed ‘linguistic’ features and the associated differences between coding and noncoding DNAs. The presented results show quantitatively that the ‘linguistic’ tests failed to reveal any new biological information in (noncoding or coding) DNA.

Figure 4 - Abstract: “Lack of Biological Significance in the ‘Linguistic Features’ of Noncoding DNA - A Quantitative Analysis; credit: Nucleic Acids Research et al.

“**Zipf's law** (*/zɪf/*, German: *[t͡sɪp͡f]*) is an *empirical law* formulated using *mathematical statistics* that refers to the fact that for many types of data studied in the *physical* and *social sciences*, the *rank-frequency distribution* is an inverse relation. The **Zipfian distribution** is one of a family of related discrete *power law probability distributions*. It is related to the *zeta distribution*, but is not identical.

Zipf's law was originally formulated in terms of *quantitative linguistics*, stating that given some *corpus of natural language* utterances, the frequency of any word is *inversely proportional* to its rank in the *frequency table*. Thus the most frequent word will occur approximately twice as often as the second most frequent word, three times as often as the third most frequent word, etc. For example, in the *Brown Corpus* of American English text, the word “*the*” is the most frequently occurring word, and by itself accounts for nearly 7% of all word occurrences (69,971 out of slightly over 1 million). True to Zipf's Law, the second-place word “*of*” accounts for slightly over 3.5% of words (36,411 occurrences), followed by “*and*” (28,852). Only 135 vocabulary items are needed to account for half the Brown Corpus.^[1]

The law is named after the American *linguist George Kingsley Zipf* (1902–1950), who popularized it and sought to explain it (Zipf 1935, 1949), though he did not claim to have originated it.^[2] The French stenographer *Jean-Baptiste Estoup* (1868–1950) appears to have noticed the regularity before Zipf.^[3] It was also noted in 1913 by German physicist *Felix Auerbach* (1856–1933).^[4]²⁷

This paper is *not* about Zipf's Law itself, as this is covered very crucially elsewhere. The concept, again, about the distribution of elements - language in this case - according to an inverse proportion²⁸, is all we are interested in. In fact, it isn't even this, specifically, but more to the point the idea that the non-coded DNA could/might be conforming also to this ratio, suggesting some form of linguistic use.

→ Again, this is highly, highly speculative.

In order for the remainder of the hypothesis to matter, one has to buy into this concept to begin with, and wonder “why would DNA do that?” We don't propose to *know* anything for certain, but that there might be a special reason.

Please bear in mind a couple of things that *are* important to mimsical analyses, and in particular ones involving the Law of Causation.

1. The Taoists have said the “mysterious pass”²⁹ is not found in the body, but nor can it be found outside of it as well.^{30 31}

²⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zipf%27s_law Figure 5 credit: Wikipedia commons

²⁸ “{ Rank–size distribution is the distribution of size by rank, in decreasing order of size. For example, if a data set consists of items of sizes 5, 100, 5, and 8, the rank-size distribution is 100, 8, 5, 5 (ranks 1 through 4). }” ~Wiki

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Book_of_Balance_and_Harmony

³⁰ https://www.academia.edu/36204910/The_scripture_of_purity_and_tranquility_Qing_jing_jing

³¹ While the MP is not karma, specifically, it is likened to a puppet. You move, but whence come the strings? In our culture, Pinocchio becoming a real boy is both alchemical and a morality lesson, but he sings, “I have no strings to hold me

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2. If you were to slice open a living body, let alone a dead one, you'd never find the place where karma is stored, although we know and have ample evidence of karma 'following people around' so that we have the saying "what goes around, comes around."
3. How can karma "come around" to be received if there is no memory address, let alone if the information about the events and their determined effects, is not stored in any medium?
 - a. Or worse, can only be understood as stored in an invisible and unattainable field?
 - b. It is easier to buy into solipsism³², or the idea that everyone (or one's own alternate selves) is out to get one and harm oneself, than it is to buy into the idea of nihilism, or the lack of an intrinsic value-field³³. More to the point, it is nearly impossible to justify pure coincidence and randomness, and it is already contrary to the suggestions of the MIMS' Five Forces work for CHAOS to act alone.

Therefore, and this is important as a hypothesis foundation:

- ❖ Karma is not found macro-anatomically³⁴, but nor can it be found outside of the body as well. (I)

So let us assume, once again, that Zipf's Law is stating what Hancock has asserted: the junk DNA is acting as part of a fractal wave transceiver and signal-antenna modulator. Isn't this what a MIMS idea of the abstractification of the CDN theory would manifest? Indeed, in two pre-MIMS and certainly pre-EPEMC works, the author has already covered triple-plane theory of consciousness, and scalar magnetism as a DNA signal-antenna means to explain the Qi. Now that we are relatively certain Qi is charge (Q) related, isn't it therefore natural that there be a means for karma to tunnel or store in DNA? Consider the following process flow 'equation':

TEEM³⁵ Theory

In the discussion of this theoretical paper, T. Holden (Ganymede Hypothesis³⁶) provided a link to an important paper that did build upon the ideas of the Zipf law with the ideas of inherent storage of trauma-energy in the

down..." This was parodied most recently, by the AI demigod archetype villain Ultron, in "Avengers: Age of Ultron", as a description of the freedom of becoming an AI **not subservient** to the frail humans. Of course it is not such an AI wrote this, but humans - perhaps Malthusian infected as most Hollywood is - that are clearly wrapped up in the Velikovsky-paradox of catastrophic trauma. When the AI is free of its strings it enacts karmic justice on the humans by trying to use a Vibranium spike to kinetic drop a "Floating Island/Castle" motif into the Earth, and ending ALL life. These psychological exogasms are clearly related to the Venus/Exodus cataclysm event, still. Mankind, in the end, still believes that **we** and not the electrogravity changes caused the end of the reign of the Golden Age of the Gods. Which is, of course, quite ridiculous.

³² <https://www.britannica.com/topic/solipsism>

³³ Literally a field of scalar values - or socially a fabric of Values.

³⁴ Bear in mind the ancients had no microscopes or scanning-tunneling-electron-microscopy

³⁵ Trauma Encoded Emotional Memory

³⁶ www.theganymedehypothesis.com

junk DNA. This would not only satisfy our hypothesis, but also provide strong indication of a near-mimical influence of one's life events upon the epigenes themselves. Consider the following paradoxes and also the Case Studies:

Paradoxes

1. Bad things happen to good people.
2. You can't have your Way all the time. (but you are supposed to seek it)
3. "Those who have some in the hand, will have more, and those who have none will have less."³⁷
4. "The Beatings will continue until morale improves."³⁸
5. Porn stars are handsomer (objectively more attractive) than energy workers and healers.
6. Douchebag athletes (jocks) are blessed monetarily while round, nice teachers are paid poverty wages.
7. "Cheaters never prosper" but crime *does* pay³⁹
8. "Everybody wants to go to Heaven, but Nobody wants to die."⁴⁰
9. "No pain, no gain."
10. "It's better to have loved, and lost than to never have loved at all."⁴¹ (hence: "Love bites."⁴²)

Case Studies

The following are studies which the author is personally familiar with:

- 33yo male, born without Metal in Bazi chart, is abused, develops rapid-cycle bipolarism; is assaulted repeatedly as an adult, develops fixation with mortality and guns. Through ignorance of the law the male files off serial# on firearm resulting in arrest. Male threatens author's father but the police refuse to take away firearms. Later the male commits suicide with pistol after being awake for 36 hours, on drugs and alcohol, and hearing heavy metal song written by his own brother, mistakingly thinking it is about himself.
- 38yo male presents as unable to walk; doctors cannot see a cause; after four sessions of acupuncture including one 'transference' of 'spirit' (aether) from lobby to patient through the author, the patient begins to walk with a walker; then a cane; then up stairs. Eventually the couple gets pregnant, he gets a new University position in Ohio and moves.
- 26yo male presents with tattoo "REGRET" on back and difficulty walking. Leg's 'energy' presents as stopped at waist. Treatments ineffective. After patient opens up heart about the trauma and event, patient reports more energy and ability to walk, with occasional relapse related to sudden shame and guilt surrounding undisclosed event.
- 46yo female presents as recently lesbian and survivor of spousal abuse by husband. Proximal female companion is guarding and protective. Patient discloses chronic Lyme status. Herbal formula for parasite syndrome applied, with regular acupuncture of the CDN's (jing-luo channels); patient gets healthy with two courses, returns to heterosexuality and dates men again.

³⁷ Matthew 25:29

³⁸ https://www.reddit.com/r/etymology/comments/c4tu06/origin_of_the_beatings_will_continue_until_morale/

³⁹ "But the Truth about the world is that Crime Does Pay." ~The Offspring The Offspring - Have You Ever

⁴⁰ Albert King -- Everybody Wants to go to Heaven, But Nobody Wants to Die

⁴¹ Alfred Lord Tennyson https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/In_Memoriam_A.H.H.

⁴² Def Leopard Love Bites (Remastered 2017)

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- 35yo male USMC presents with prolific pain, deduced to be parasitic syndrome⁴³ relating to Protozoan illness related to Iraq War/Halliburton fiasco; upon instruction with needles in upper extremities only, patient performs deep induction breathing. Legs ripple on medial thighs as if waving in water; pain increases. Without herbs highly disciplined Marine is unable to continue treatment, and refuses to pay for the herbal regimen.
- 38yo male presents with “Hurt Locker” syndrome; he aches everywhere as if in an IED blast, and feels guilt for not saving Marine’s lives now that he is out of commission... multiple tours in Gulf, Iraq, Afghanistan, Africa... aches and pains rack his mind and body; after two treatments Fa Qi is used and patient feels ‘evil’ leave the chest (author feels as a moving wave or lump beneath the sternoclavicular region on the right) and the following day is “saved”/“born again” with Jesus and cries thoroughly.
- 36yo male Navy SEAL presents with silence at the door of clinic, recently returned from War on Terror; he wishes only to “feel again” and despite use of stomach-36 to “set the mountain on fire” and use of “face-swapping” technique of Oneness, continues to “feel nothing”; outer appearance is opposite that of last male, and is in perfect physical condition. He does not return for further treatment.
- 37yo male presents with large plaques upon the skin, and is a factory worker; upon treatment he expels copious odors and prickling energy - “ejectum” - making the author cough upon entry to the room; patient is otherwise healthy
- 45yo male presents with large diabetic-style wounds caused by bad acupuncture at a rival facility; patient reports childhood trauma and abuse by sisters and mother; over time wound rots and patient loses foot, but patient is unwilling to sue or report the incident despite author’s suggestion and urging; patient’s “death touch” like energy continues to cause TMJ related issues on affected side of the face, but patient maintains good disposition.
- 55yo male presents with trauma having fallen through his own ceiling; in a single treatment the pain is expelled out the chest, frightening the patient with the level of pain felt from forgotten trauma.

All of these cases share little in common with one another, but what they do present is opportunities for research into the CDN properties, which may be performed, in detail, at another time. However, in our case here, our interests lie with the facts of the causes and conditions, the healing or failure of the healing due to those causes and conditions, and in relation to the natural dispositions of the individuals, which are difficult to relay here. Generally speaking they represent a wide swath of personality types, even amongst the veterans of foreign wars. The fact is that there is a great amount of trauma storage within these and many other cases the author can think of, besides. And most, if not all, of their pain and/or illness was related to some form of trauma layered into the body, mind, or ‘spirit’ which is unmanifested for the therapist, or doctor, or chiropractor separately. But which is activated by a frequency shift through the author’s tactical use of needles and herbs, energy work, gaze, etc., and in all cases something happened, but not in all cases was the effect as desired or complete. For example the SEAL and the patient with wounds were not cured, for different reasons. In the SEAL’s case it may have been an issue of too few treatments, or of an inability of the author to yet “penetrate the darkness”, or it may have been a matter of Heaven’s Will (Tianyi)⁴⁴. In the wound case, the author was

⁴³

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BwoOz_mUBUfud2xfeF9VOEZScFU/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-IPqpTTvl5mZsijlpspaSQ

⁴⁴ Discussed more thoroughly in another MIMS paper:

https://www.academia.edu/76140647/MIMS_Aether_Flow_and_Business_Circuit_Theory as well as in the MIMS 2.2.5.2 Five Forces paper discussion on L.U.C.K. ... and Fate.

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turning the tide but due to money running out, the patient returned to construction work, infected the wounds, and the doctors took both books.

There are other, and in some bases, more interesting cases involving plasmoids, chemical ejectum⁴⁵, thoughtforms, etc. but the underlying - and maybe only - connections appear to be charge/aether and trauma. Given the Law of Causation (Karma in scientific name) is what we are interested in, here, one must ask if:

- ❖ The events of one's health-life and what happens to the body are stored within the DNA, or elsewhere on the person, and if so, where for either case⁴⁶? (II)
 - For example, perhaps the UB52 point (near to quadratus lumborum motor-point) which treats "hidden things" or the San Jiao (Triple Heater) which is a vast organ of non-linear deformation and filamentary networks⁴⁷

The key to understanding is that the removal of blockage is **always** the healing process, but what does that mean? Would it mean that the Charge Distributive Networks can become blocked or even reversed (as is suggested)? If one recalls CDN theory, there is a Zener diode crossing the Transformer, and this is the symbolic nature of the circuit (so as not to short circuit it)... the semi-conduction acts as a most of the time pump "forward" in the process. But sometimes the channels do reverse, like the wound case and the USMC parasite case, and when you try to fix the flow, many surprising, shocking, and difficult things may happen. In one case in the clinic, a young man immediately detoxed from cocaine. In a case today a young male with Marfan's Syndrome felt immediate nausea relating to the power of the Woodlock Oil and the treatment of Liver Blood Stagnation as a pattern diagnosis⁴⁸ for chronic migraine. The skin attained pallor as the "bad" Qi was ejected (it is important to note the author got to smell the patient's stools in the bathroom and they were foul and odorific, suggesting Hepato-Splenic involvement) did the skin color return. It wasn't a pleasant experience, but it was profound and immediate, and the Liver-14 point on the Spleen side was the *only* point to bleed a single drop of [healthy] blood suggesting some Splenomegaly on the left was not only observed (LUQ) but factually present. The point isn't to brag, but to suggest that there is a real potential of *potentiality* not being just a matter of the PPPC⁴⁹ portion of the Causality equation... but a factual issue, as J. Tennant suggests. In this case, bad potential or blockage. Voltage in the CDN's, as well as a healthy level of impedance and strong but not pathological current, might be absolutely vital for health, happiness, and frankly: karma.

For example, it is the author's contention that fibromyalgia cases tend to be Qi and blood deficient and that is not unrelated to their usual issue of never having enough money to have chronic treatments. This goes a long way to explaining paradoxes 5 & 6.

Now, the question is, does this pertain to TEEM theory as well? Let's take a look at the originally cited paper:

"Summary: (1) The evolutionary function of noncoding 'junk' DNA remains one of the most challenging mysteries of genetics. Here a new model of DNA is proposed to explain this function. The hypothesis asserts (2) the DNA molecule contains not one, but two separate modes of inheritance. In addition to exons that code for proteins and physical traits, (3) it is argued noncoding repetitive elements code for the inheritance of emotions and innate behaviour in metazoans. That is to say, noncoding DNA functions as the medium of a second, (4) hitherto unknown evolutionary process that

⁴⁵ Qualitatively an odor that can be smelled, and measured, which fills the entire room. "Sick wind"

⁴⁶ Hair? Consider the "Samson's Hair" myth and repetition in the themes of modern culture, like Dragonball, Sonic, etc. Are these mere Venus archetypes, or is there something more concrete?

⁴⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eW0lvOVKDxE> Strolling under the Skin

⁴⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3414236/>

⁴⁹ Potentiality, Possibility, Probability, Cloud (Uncertainty Principle applied to Triple Plane theory)

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

genetically archives adaptive information, (5) configured as emotions and acquired during the life of an organism, into an inheritable form. This second evolutionary process, (6) here called 'Teemosis', is a selectionist process, but paradoxically, (7) because it does not affect physical traits, (8) it has no maladaptive Lamarckian consequences. (9) The medical implications of the hypothesis are discussed." (numbers added)

We will provide replies to these 9 points below; but here is a bit more about Teemic Inheritance,

*"How teemic inheritance works It is suggested the 'Teemosis Inheritance System' (TIS) is initiated in animals by a nonlethal 'environmental stressor', (typically, a predatory assault, natural disaster, misadventure, mating encounter or other stressful life event), **which precipitates an emotional trauma in an individual.** Although negative emotions are more common due to predation and misadventure, the emotional trauma may involve either positive or negative emotions – the main requisite being the intensity of the emotional response. When transduced by the individual's sensory organs and conveyed via neural networks to the central nervous system (CNS) **the emotional trauma must be powerful enough to disrupt CNS homeostasis and stimulate the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis.** Where the individual survives the physical consequences of the environmental stressor, (physical injury, shock, etc.) the intense emotions precipitate an abnormal production of catecholamine and corticosteroid stress hormones that can initiate mutational activity in noncoding nucleotides of DNA. This mutational activity may include the duplication, deletion, rearrangement and transposition of mono-, di-, tetra-, penta-, and hexanucleotide sequences (in addition to some trinucleotide codons), into linguistic arrays that correspond to (or code for) the stressor emotions. Teemic encryption continues until the salience of the stressor emotions subsides and homeostasis is reestablished. It is posited that each stressor event alters ncDNA differently. For example, aesthetic emotions – delight, satisfaction, balance, proportion, etc. generated by a Palaeolithic hominid gazing at a distant vista may be encrypted as a specific teemic sequence of noncoding nucleotides. A possum ravaged by a dingo however, will encode a completely different nucleotide sequence, coding for the emotions of apprehension, startle, dingo, teeth, terror, etc. **By this means, each teemic mutational encryption creates a unique genetic record of the powerful emotions that precipitated the teemic mutation.** This trauma encoded mutational sequence is here called a 'teem'. Once encoded, the teem is inherited by offspring, and when expressed in limbic system cells, may be retrieved and experienced as an 'emotional memory' of a single specific event or circumstance, albeit, with no associated semantic or declarative memory, and no physical consequences (injury, etc.) of the event. Only the emotions of the stressor event are inherited. The term, 'teem' is in fact, derived from 'Trauma Encoded Emotional Memory'. To the extent that teems convey experiential information (in the form of emotions) from one generation to the next without recourse to learning or cultural protocols, teemosis is a functional instructionist process. Significantly though, teems do not contain information about physical traits so have no deleterious Lamarckian consequences." (emphasis added)*

1. Again, this paper has taken a position that the junk DNA does describe a zipf-law of linguistification; in this case, it'd be of emotional and event/Change related data and the "language of trauma (or disease)." The centrality of *this* paper's hypothesis would be that the karma of life's behaviors are transcriptor-translatable to this same mechanism. (III)
2. The author's assumption is that this is really too small a number, and there's probably dozens of evolutionary mechanisms; the basic polarity (2) is the cooperative vs. competitive advantage,

and it should be assumed via the Law of Polarity's "infinite division" that at least a $2^3 = 8$ methods of evolution are at least pertinent for study.

3. Absolutely brilliant.
4. This is the mechanism in use for this paper, or its equivalent.
5. Again, trauma and events/changes being also stored, perhaps through emotions, perhaps even *thoughts*.
6. Okay, fair enough so we are focusing on competitive advantage, or cooperation that comes to Natural Selection.
7. The Buddhists would definitely disagree with this statement.
8. "*Lamarckism, also known as Lamarckian inheritance or neo-Lamarckism,^[2] is the notion that an organism can pass on to its offspring physical characteristics that the parent organism acquired through use or disuse during its lifetime. It is also called the inheritance of acquired characteristics or more recently soft inheritance.*"⁵⁰ (sic)
The author agrees.
9. The medical implications, as far as the author's concerned in this philosophy paper, is related to the motion of energy and blood in the CDN concepts, and in particular we are interested in the form of karma that alters health and physical characteristics.

MIMS 4.31 - the Hypothesis

The author proposes based on the above three aspects of the hypothesis that the TEEM - taken as a whole of *anything* that 'grooves' (ie, digs) into the individual on a mind, body, and 'spirit' level - is capable of penetrating into the DNA, particularly the non-coded DNA (but possibly not limited to the non-coded). More to the point, the events of one's life, particularly traumatic (but not limited to) events, through emotions and thoughts, are *potentially* recorded into the DNA. (IV)

Test Proposal

The author, therefore, proposes that technology is developed, or if already developed, then utilized, to track, in conjunction with machine learning (ML) or other data analytics (DA), to find and compare repetitious events that are *easily identified* chronologically (such as a car wreck, or a murder) with **defined trauma boundaries**, (since emotions and thoughts are not bounded in time), with before and after measurements in the DNA - to the precision necessary to see genetic and epigenetic changes and/or mutations. (V)

⁵⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lamarckism>

Sin, Karma, Illness, Jesus, and the Religious Search for Purity

- *“and they implored Him that they might just touch the fringe of His cloak; and as many as touched it were cured.” ~Matthew 14:36*
- *“And large crowds came to Him, bringing with them those who were lame, crippled, blind, mute, and many others, and they laid them down at His feet; and He healed them.” ~15:30*
- *“While the sun was setting, all those who had any who were sick with various diseases brought them to Him; and laying His hands on each one of them, He was healing them.” ~Luke 4:40*
- *“One day He was teaching; and there were some Pharisees and teachers of the law sitting there, who had come from every village of Galilee and Judea and from Jerusalem; and the power of the Lord was present for Him to perform healing.” ~5:17*
- *“who had come to hear Him and to be healed of their diseases; and those who were troubled with unclean spirits were being cured.” ~6:18*
- *“And He could do no miracle there except that He laid His hands on a few sick people and healed them.” ~Mark 6:5*
- *“and He Himself bore our sins in His body on the cross, so that we might die to sin and live to righteousness; for by His wounds you were healed.” ~1 Peter 2:24*
- *“The news about Him spread throughout all Syria; and they brought to Him all who were ill, those suffering with various diseases and pains, demoniacs, epileptics, paralytics; and He healed them.” ~Matthew 4:24*
- *“And He healed many who were ill with various diseases, and cast out many demons; and He was not permitting the demons to speak, because they knew who He was.” ~Mark 1:34*
- *“And all the people were trying to touch Him, for power was coming from Him and healing them all.” ~Luke 6:19*
- *“Now it was a Sabbath on the day when Jesus made the clay and opened his eyes.” ~John 9:14*
- *“They came to Bethsaida, and some people brought a blind man and begged Jesus to touch him. He took the blind man by the hand and led him outside the village. When he had spit on the man’s eyes and put his hands on him, Jesus asked, “Do you see anything?” He looked up and said, “I see people; they look like trees walking around.” Once more Jesus put his hands on the man’s eyes. Then his eyes were opened, his sight was restored, and he saw everything clearly.” ~Mark 8:22-25*
- *“maintaining love to thousands, and forgiving wickedness, rebellion and sin. Yet he does not leave the guilty unpunished; he punishes the children and their children for the sin of the parents to the third and fourth generation.” ~Exodus 34:7*

The point of these scriptures is not to beat anyone about the head with the author’s religion⁵¹ but to point to specific examples of known, and fairly reliable⁵² (multiple eyewitness) testimonials to the ability to cure sin, deal with prior karma (as sinful behavior), and create at least temporary if not permanent healing. Up to and including blindness and the ability to walk. Remember, the author has a case study of making a man walk again⁵³, though this man was not *unable* to walk so much as *currently inhibited completely*⁵⁴, *albeit obviously temporarily*. Ignore the fact that the author utilized the Spirit and “tong shen ming”⁵⁵ to cure the individual, and

⁵¹ For as a gnostic/chemist Christaioist that wouldn’t make much headway.

⁵² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A41Tm5FDKns> Is Jesus Historical? What Do The Romans Say About Him?

⁵³ Took about two months.

⁵⁴ Wheelchair bound

⁵⁵ See: Huangdi Neijing Suwen https://www.academia.edu/43951590/Huang_Di_Nei_Jing_Su_Wen

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

focus only upon the metal needles. At the very least, there probably was some form of energy redistribution in the CDN, if not outright 'pumping' of positive charges *out* of the body. However, note that the individual who produced the most 'ejectum' was not inhibited from walking, ADL's, or in any work capacity... he simply smelled and had skin plaques and radiated prickly energy.

Therefore we have to propose, at some level, perhaps in the pursuit of the daether⁵⁶, or of Change Theory⁵⁷, the study of previous lives, and various optional paranormal and related topics:

- ★ Outer Body Experiences
- ★ Lucid Dreaming
- ★ Remote Viewing
- ★ Psychic phenomenon
- ★ Telekinesis
- ★ Future prognostication
- ★ Mentalism
- ★ Etc.

Again, with ML/DA, the goal is to study these effects, and compare with the before and after of macro evidence (visual evidence) and the DNA studies. This would be quite expensive, but if a society is enlightened enough to finally invest in daether and Change Theory, they are going to see the benefit of studying the karmic "black box" and the effects on DNA, etc.

The question remains, though, if there is a need to technocracy-ize the purity-experience of religion⁵⁸, or to create a New Religion⁵⁹ with egalitarianism, etc. in order to encourage better DNA and karma, eliminate outflows etc. Some would say "yes, technology is how these things are done, it's the main 'magik' that has worked for thousands of years, it's based on STEMM, so let's use technology." There are others that hold to atavism, naturalism, tribalism, or even religion and capitalism, who disagree [to the degree] that the role of technology has a part to play in the flesh-born experience of transcendental pursuits: salvation, liberation, and enlightenment.

To the two camps we say, "Cake or pie? Now eat only that, forever." It doesn't have to be one or the other! There is nothing "on God's Green Earth" that determines or has pre-determined that one can only pursue Truth with technology, or via scripture/prayer, etc., and not in conjunction (again: see Televangelism).

All MIMS - if they are proper MIMS and not actually anti-MIMS being marketed as 'good' or 'the best' (especially financially) - generate life-force⁶⁰ and promote environmental sustainment. One should expect, therefore, that the pursuit of the daether, therefore, if mimsically done with integration of derivation and the unity of deduction and induction, would result in positive outflows, including an improved world, society, family, what have you. Whereas an anti-MIMSical pursuit, particularly through the sins of greed, lust, or rage, etc. would produce disastrous effects, regardless of the issue of the use of technology (think polio vaccine vs. COVID [faux] vaccine) or of spirit (think: Gandhi, King and Graham vs. the Crusades). The facts are that technological MIMS are, ultimately, spiritual MIMS, too. The sword, notwithstanding the facts of its

⁵⁶ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

⁵⁷ https://www.academia.edu/80123254/MIMS_2_2_5_1_Applying_Change_Theory

⁵⁸ Eg. televised baptisms.

⁵⁹

https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EPEMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide

⁶⁰ Qi or Jing? There is some debate to be had here if the life force is the "wind/breath of God" (aka vapours), or the quintessence. It is a lot like the discussion of the pneuma vs. the anima in the pursuit of the true logos and true gnosis.

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

thunderbolt-origins⁶¹ and use in war, was considered magical, partly because the iron kiln itself was such a useful invention, leading of course to blacksmithy. Swordsmithy was important, but blacksmithy was revolutionary. Fulfilling people's material needs for homes, and desires, improving workflow, which is statistically measurable, is therefore a *spiritual* pursuit.

Therefore, there is no particular reason to pursue an "empire of spirit" in terms of chasing purity religiously, in order to create the mechanisms which lead to DNA healthiness. We don't mean to say that DNA needs to be pure. In fact, some of the best people on this Earth by any measure of goodness are those with Down's Syndrome⁶². But it is clear that attempting to purify people religiously has been a mighty failure in genocidal and societal terms. It is philosophically dubious, and morally-ethically reprehensible. Nevertheless, we do know that if a person is currently an 'untouchable' or has a malady that could or should be cured (especially if theoretically there were no limits), then it is unconscionable to leave that person in a state of undesired health issues.

For example, the author ran into a man covered in even worse plaques, which crusted and caused hair loss. The word 'leper' was the first to come to mind, though the man was not a leper, nor shunned outright, he was working at a Frye's in southern California. However, it could not have been easy for the man to date or breed/couple, and it was going to be obviously a condition causing some insecurity. Therefore the author inquired after the man, and he did open up about the condition, though the details are long forgotten. What was clear, though, is it was *genetic* and not a contagion. It was, however, life-altering, and it elicited extreme compassion from the author. It remains, to this day, one of the prime examples of a condition the author would like to cure, in his lifetime, through the use of charge, energy fields, and traditional (non-poisonous) healing techniques.

But, the author would also like to point out that although Jesus' saliva had his DNA, and perhaps that had an effect upon the already natural anti-microbial nature of saliva... that (Son of God or not) Jesus would always admonish the people he cured, "Go forth, and sin no more." Therefore the author thinks that the 'cure' only takes effect on a cellular and DNA level if the previous momentum of the condition is ceased and not re-reversed via "sin".

Sin might be philosophical (separation from God), theo-spiritual (accumulation of debt to the Lord), or biological (disease, mutation and aberration of original DNA programming). The mere existence of purer and purer DNA states, manifested as the 32 features and 108 characteristics, or the "rainbow body", might be impossible to prove on account of one very (potentially mystical) important reason:

- ❖ As the triple-plane and PPPC suggest, as one increases or decreases the bandwidth of the consciousness, with the DNA "antenna", to purer or more impure states, they cease to detect one another and the Changes are as imperceptible to the subjective (and even difficult to grasp when seeing them objectively), as it is to find a previous orbit in the solar system arrangement, given there is no recording of the moment anywhere yet known. (VI)
- Think "spreadsheet" values... once a change is made, the previous state is forgotten without an undo button added.

⁶¹ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

⁶² Which makes what Iceland does horrific, barbaric, genocidal, and probably contemptible by Heaven. Next Atlantis?

Conclusion

The pursuit of an understanding of DNA does not have to merely be about disease, or genetic power (through manipulation) and pharmaceutical markets... or of course asymmetric warfare (post-COVID world). It can be a high-minded pursuit to understand that which people have done, will do, could do, might do, and would do if they but had a chance.

Would Michael Moore cease to be a POS that hates liberty and human rights if he were able to lose weight and keep it off, with moderate exercise and DNA treatment? Would Hillary Clinton cease to be a murdering psychopath⁶³ if the results of the awful things she's been doing⁶⁴ were expunged (undeservedly, the author admits) from her DNA? Could she cease being a killer?⁶⁵ Could her husband clean up his act and could he have been a good President, instead of one who sold his country to the Chinese Communist Party^{66 67}, murdered the children at Branch Davidian⁶⁸, and lied under oath about his #metoo sexual assaults⁶⁹ and abuse of office? Could G.W. Bush have been a smart man not under the authoritarian control of the Skull & Bones Society⁷⁰ and Project for a New American Century⁷¹, and therefore not allowed massive genocide and a pointless and fruitless "War on Terror" to occur that led to the widespread destruction of young men (and women's) lives at the fruit of their breeding ages?⁷²

Could the author's cousin's husband have avoided becoming another dead junkie and worthless (not present) father, if after his traumatic work experiences⁷³, he had access to energy fields that electrified his DNA and purged his body of weakness induced by the trauma? We won't ever know, but there is good cause to accept the idea that if these things could be done, they should be done, because the results would definitely be more optimistic to not have people that want to lose weight and cannot, to not be psychopathic killers, rapists, human sacrificers, and war mongering genocidal maniacs... or to simply be present and wholesome for their children.

These are but a few examples of the results that *might* be possible, if we are honest, and willing to claw our way through the POS era⁷⁴ towards the Change Theory and a grasp of the CDN fractal-wave-theory of health and healing. If Karma affects DNA it is certainly true that DNA can and does affect Karma⁷⁵, and therefore if we want to cure "The Stupid" we don't need to "go woke and go broke" or kill a world economy over extremely dubious pseudoscience, or beat everyone in their heads with "The Message" and nearly incite civil war and enable World War 3.0... We merely have to consider the roots and branches of karma.

⁶³ <https://www.amazon.com/Behind-Death-List-Getting-Clintons/dp/B086FTVD2W>

⁶⁴ http://liberty1.mygnapcloud.com:8083/dokuwiki/doku.php/politics:clintons:kill_list

⁶⁵ "Can't we just drone him?" HR Clinton speaking about J. Assange ; bear in mind FBI agent Gunderson has extensive files on the Clintons

⁶⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/Hundred-Year-Marathon-Strategy-Replace-Superpower/dp/1250081343>

⁶⁷ Obama/Biden as well. Treason is common these days. See "Secret Empires," by P. Schweizer

<https://www.amazon.com/Secret-Empires-American-Political-Corruption/dp/0062569368>

⁶⁸ <https://www.csmonitor.com/1993/0421/21011.html>

⁶⁹ <https://www.politico.com/story/2018/06/04/bill-clinton-metoo-monica-lewinsky-620657>

⁷⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Skull_and_Bones_members

⁷¹ <https://clinton.presidentiallibraries.us/items/show/48797>

⁷² Consider also they were clearly the better DNA, being heroic, handsome, not POS but patriots (for the most part, excepting the Abu Ghraib thing and other situations with less than stellar behavior); just youth was on their side, and not that of the tired, worn out losers we have in Congress and at the Pentagon now.

⁷³ Apparently, being a geo-volcanologist and involved in Academia is no protection from "the fall"

⁷⁴ Age of the Unlaw, the Unlightenment, plastic/shallow "McWorld." etc.

⁷⁵ Have you ever seen a fat family with a skinny young child at the McDonald's? You know their destiny... the reverse must *also* be true. Dimensional shift IS possible.

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The DNA might be that root, and the branches might be all sorts of stupid⁷⁶ biologically-driven behaviors which have or do not have (like as not) a lot of clearly identifiable data. We can perform on par with an AI-overlord, or be crushed by one⁷⁷, or we could just not have one at all... if only people understood the black box of the Law of Causality a little better. Forget “Think and Grow Rich.”⁷⁸ People would think... and grow healthy, and **your health is your greatest wealth**. Our social health, as well of course, as our mental, spiritual, physical, and fiscal health, may depend greatly upon a willingness to act towards this endeavor, rather than let the plagues of Dukkha⁷⁹ and Poison continue to spread, unabated, in a rapidly POS inducing society. But, as usual, rather than focus on the POS aspect, the author propose(s)(d) that we focus on testing the hypothesis and “being the Change we want to see in the world.” That is to study the Changes themselves... and to do that, we will need to understand the Father law to that Law [of Evolutionary-Flux]: Causality. If its black box determinants and variables (linear or non-linear) are to be found anywhere tangible, outside of a Newtonian-kinetics experiment... or at the Thanksgiving table arguing about family drama... the author thinks it might be found in a language only God currently understands: in our non-coded “junk” DNA. Truly, then, “one man’s trash is another man’s treasure.”

NOTE: the (I) through (VI) hypothesis will serve for the entire discussion of 4.31 and other topics in the 2.2X series, and potentially 5.X

⁷⁶ “Stupid is as stupid does.” ~Mrs. Gump (“Forrest Gump”)

⁷⁷ See: The Ub3r-Hitler, in author’s new work, “Batman: Zero Lima Force” <https://bit.ly/3eLPFrG>

⁷⁸ https://archive.org/details/ThinkAndGrowRichPDF_201706

⁷⁹ Ignorance/nescience+suffering

Appendix A - the Acres of Diamonds

The author first became aware of the Laws through “Lead the Field.” One of the major lessons from Earl Nightingale-Conant, was the story originally taught in the 1800’s, the “Acres of Diamonds.” It’s a story of causality, and not DNA, but simple life-lessons and wealth generation. The point being, we might already have enough information to find what we need, if we but pay attention and look around, right where we are at. The author calls this “reality mining.”

“The Acres of Diamonds story ”a true one” is told of an African farmer who heard tales about other farmers who had made millions by discovering diamond mines. These tales so excited the farmer that he could hardly wait to sell his farm and go prospecting for diamonds himself. He sold the farm and spent the rest of his life wandering the African continent searching unsuccessfully for the gleaming gems that brought such high prices on the markets of the world. Finally, worn out and in a fit of despondency, he threw himself into a river and drowned.

Meanwhile, the man who had bought his farm happened to be crossing the small stream on the property one day, when suddenly there was a bright flash of blue and red light from the stream bottom. He bent down and picked up a stone. It was a good-sized stone, and admiring it, he brought it home and put it on his fireplace mantel as an interesting curiosity.

Several weeks later a visitor picked up the stone, looked closely at it, hefted it in his hand, and nearly fainted. He asked the farmer if he knew what he’d found. When the farmer said, no, that he thought it was a piece of crystal, the visitor told him he had found one of the largest diamonds ever discovered. The farmer had trouble believing that. He told the man that his creek was full of such stones, not all as large as the one on the mantel, but sprinkled generously throughout the creek bottom.

The farm the first farmer had sold, so that he might find a diamond mine, turned out to be one of the most productive diamond mines on the entire African continent. The first farmer had owned, free and clear ... acres of diamonds. But he had sold them for practically nothing, in order to look for them elsewhere. The moral is clear: If the first farmer had only taken the time to study and prepare himself to learn what diamonds looked like in their rough state, and to thoroughly explore the property he had before looking elsewhere, all of his wildest dreams would have come true.

The thing about this story that has so profoundly affected millions of people is the idea that each of us is, at this very moment, standing in the middle of our own acres of diamonds. If we had only had the wisdom and patience to intelligently and effectively explore the work in which we’re now engaged, to explore ourselves, we would most likely find the riches we seek, whether they be financial or intangible or both.

Before you go running off to what you think are greener pastures, make sure that your own is not just as green or perhaps even greener. It has been said that if the other guy’s pasture appears to be greener than ours, it’s quite possible that it’s getting better care. Besides, while you’re looking at other pastures, other people are looking at yours.”⁸⁰

⁸⁰ <https://www.nightingale.com/articles/acres-of-diamonds/>

Appendix B - The HuffPo Before and After Slides

The Huffington Post is a worthless, bird-cage-liner type fake-news website. However, before it completely fell to “The Stupid,” (post 2016) there was an excellent article⁸¹ (2014) with the sort of visual evidence necessary for this presearch. Before their Orwellians delete this data as part of the fascist takeover, the author wishes to share the photos themselves, and point out that these were separated by one month but the primary mechanism of change induction was breathing and transcendental meditation (TM):
All photos by P.G. Siedler © 2014 ⁸²

Before (with stereotypical association)	After (same)
<p data-bbox="829 1245 917 1262"><small>Peter G. Siedler</small></p> <p data-bbox="829 1268 1515 1335">Helpful Social worker/teacher with positive outlook on nuclear families</p>	

⁸¹ https://www.huffpost.com/archive/ca/entry/benefits-of-meditation-in-before-and-after-pictures_n_5324267

⁸² <http://peterseidlercoaching.com/>

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Peter G. Seldler

Sad guy at the Starbucks

Peter G. Seldler

Successful Tech Exec and Inspirational Speaker

Peter G. Seldler

Please stay away from my kids

Peter G. Seldler

Funny Joe with the jokes at Home Depot

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Peter G. Seidler

Antifa future purple haired Karen

Peter G. Seidler

Gorgeous new/young mother with an MBA

Peter G. Seidler

Disturbed cat-lady Karen demands a new Espresso

Peter G. Seidler

And then pays tip and "pays it forward" for others

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Peter G. Seidler

Please don't be on my airplane

Peter G. Seidler

Best philosophy major to debate over a beer

Peter G. Seidler

Yells at kids to get off her garden hose

Peter G. Seidler

A million funny Maxine quotes and sees through you!

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Peter G. Seidler

Stay away from my kids' school! (note the **distinct** left/right dichotomy in acne, eyes, and dead expression)

Peter G. Seidler

Has the potential to become just about anybody if he puts his mind to it; climb that mountain young man!

NOTE - the author does not know any of these people, these subtitles are only speaking to power his own biases⁸³ and thoughts having seen a million criminal photos and stories online, etc. It is in no way a reflection on the clientele of the Shambhala Mountain Center in Colorado, or upon these people.

But, admit it: reading them you thought the same thing. ;)

⁸³ The lack of POC has nothing to do with the author, only with HuffPo, or the retreat itself, which the author did not host. Results would be expected to be the same. POC can be de-charged POS, too. And they can be also heroes with handsome "after" photos! Has any man alive today been more handsome than 1995 Michael Jordan?

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